

Prevalence of Isolated Hypertension among Elderly Patients Attending a Peripheral Health Center Affiliated with A Tertiary Care Hospital in India**Bhaskar Prasad Singh¹, Amrendra Narayan Chaudhary², Jolly³, Kamran Fazal⁴**¹Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur²Associate Professor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur³Tutor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, JLNMC, Bhagalpur

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Abstract:**Background:** In this modern era, chronic non communicable diseases (NCDs) are a major global health challenge with numerous grave complications on the human body. Old age population tends to carry risk of almost all kind of diseases including non-communicable diseases. Hypertension is one of biggest well known risk factor for many of non-communicable diseases usually found in the outdoor patients.**Method:** This cross sectional study was undertaken to provide the data on the Prevalence & Pattern of hypertension amongst patients who were aged 60 years & above and who attended the Out Patients Department of the Rural Health & Training Centre of tertiary care hospital of Bihar.**Results:** Majority of patients belonging to age group 60-69 years were found to be diastolic hypertensive (24.46%). Majority of male patients were found to be diastolic hypertensive (28.43%) (P< 0.05). More or less same trend was found among female patients.**Conclusion:** Hypertension was found to be highly prevalent among the outdoor elderly patients of Rural Health & Training Centre, This study warrants the need of an early detection of hypertension, which can be accomplished by a periodic screening of the people.**Keywords:** Hypertension; Elderly; India.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

In this modern era, chronic noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) are a major global health challenge with numerous grave complications on the human body. NCDs kill 40 million people each year, equivalent to 70% of all deaths globally. Each year, 15 million people die from a NCD between the ages of 30 and 69 years; over 80% of these premature deaths occur in low and middle income countries. [1]

Hypertension is the most common disorder which is being encountered in the outdoor patients [2]. It is an established major risk factor and a leading cause of cardiovascular diseases worldwide. The prevalence of hypertension and its complications are increasing in the developing countries [3]. Cardiovascular diseases will be the largest cause of death and disability in India by 2020 [4]. The economic development, changes in the lifestyle and diet, and an increase in the life expectancy may be attributed to this rapid increase. Hypertension is an iceberg disease. The proportion of the awareness, treatment, and the control of hypertension are unacceptably low in the Indian adult population, as indicated from a plethora of studies [5-8]. Hypertension is emerging out as a major public health problem. The

prevalence of hypertension has significantly increased more among urban communities than rural people. The prevalence of hypertension will increase even further, unless broad and effective preventive measures are implemented. Prevention programmes and policies are in their infancy in India. Epidemiological studies are urgently needed to assess the prevalence of hypertension to determine the baseline, against which the future trends in the risk factor levels can be assessed and preventive strategies can be planned to promote health among the populations. [9]

Material and Methods

Observational secondary data based study, Study period June 2018 to August 2020 covering a total of 245 (Male 102 & Female 143) patients aged 60 years & above. All the patients visited RHTC (Rural Health Training Centre) of JLNMC & Hospital), Bihar, Bhagalpur. aged 60 years & above. A total of 245 patients were selected as sample size, who visited the RHTC during study period.

Inclusion criteria: All the adults who were aged 60 years & above., who attended the Rural Health

Training Centre of JLMC & Hospital, Bihar, Bha-
galpur.

Exclusion criteria: All the participants who were aged less than 60 years of age were excluded from the study. The patients who were non co-operative and those who refused to provide the necessary information were also excluded.

This study was conducted between June 2018 and August 2020. A total of 245 patients (102 males, 143 females) gave their consent and participated in the study. A structured, pretested proforma was used to collect the data with regards to the socio- demographic characteristics and the blood pressure pattern. Blood pressure was measured by the trained staff in a bid to avoid any measurement bias. Calibrated BP instrument was used throughout the study period in a bid to curtail any instrumental bias. Two measurements of the blood pressure of each study participant were made 30 minutes apart, with the participants in the sitting position, by using a mercury column sphygmomanometer. The blood pressure measurements were made on the subject's left arm by using a cuff of the appropriate size, at the level of the heart. The cuff pressure was inflated 30 mm Hg above the level at which the radial pulse disappeared and then it was deflated slowly at the rate of about 2mm per sec. In the cases where the two readings differed by over 10 mm of Hg, a third reading was obtained, and average of three measurements was taken. The pressures, at which the sound appeared and disappeared, were taken as the Systolic Blood Pressure (SBP) and the Diastolic Blood Pressure (DBP) respectively.

Operational Definitions: [10]

*Persons in the age group of 18–59 years having systolic BP \geq 140 mmHg and diastolic BP

\geq 90 mmHg or any level of BP in patients taking antihypertensive medication were considered as hypertensive.

*Persons in the age group of 60 or more than 60 years having systolic BP \geq 150 mmHg and diastolic BP \geq 90 mmHg or any level of BP in patients taking antihypertensive medication were considered as hypertensive.

Data collected were compiled and analyzed using suitable Statistical Software. The study was done using 95% confidence level. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Pearson's Chi-square test was used to evaluate differences between groups for categorized variables.

Results

This study was conducted on elderly Patients (Age 60 years & above) visited the Rural Health and training Centre. During the study period a total of 245 patients visited the health facility. Out of these all patients majority of patients were females (58.36%) and by far age distribution is concerned majority of patients (76.73%) were in the age group of 60 to 69 years. Association of age with systolic blood pressure was found to be non-significant ($P > 0.05$). On the other hand association gender with systolic blood pressure was also found to be non significant ($P > 0.05$). (Table: 1)

Table 1: Showing Association of socio demographic characteristics with systolic blood pressure

Age group (in years)	Systolic Blood pressure (in mmHg)				Total N(%)
	<120 N(%)	120-139N(%)	140-149N(%)	>150N(%)	
60-69	47(25)	87(46.27)	32(17)	22(11.7)	188 (76.73)
70 & above	19(33.33)	21(36.84)	05(8.77)	12(21.05)	57 (23.26)
Total	66(26.93)	108(44.08)	37(15.10)	34(13.87)	245 (100)
Chi square:6.74 & P value: 0.0807 (> 0.05)					
Gender					
Male	32(31.37)	(42.15)	14(13.72)	13(12.74)	102(41.63)
Female	34(23.77)	65(45.45)	23(16.08)	21(8.57)	143 (58.36)
Total	66(26.93)	108(44.08)	37(15.10)	34(13.87)	(100)
Chi square: 1.80 & P value: 0.614 (> 0.05)					

Study has also tried to find out Association of diastolic blood pressure with age and gender. No significant association was found out of diastolic blood pressure with both age ($P > 0.05$) and Gender respectively ($P > 0.05$). (Table: 2)

Table 2: Showing Association of socio demographic characteristics with diastolic blood pressure

Age group (in years)	Diastolic Blood pressure (in mmHg)				Total N (%)
	<8N (%)	89-89 N (%)	9099N(%)	>100 N (%)	
60-69	74(39.36)	68(36.17)	38(20.21)	08(4.25)	188 (76.73)
70 & above	22(38.59)	19(33.33)	10(17.54)	06(10.52)	57 (23.26)
Total	96(39.18)	87(35.51)	48(19.59)	14(5.71)	245 (100)
Chi square:3.27 & P value: 0.351 (> 0.05)					

Gender					
Male	35(34.31)	38(37.25)	20(19.60)	09(8.82)	102(41.63)
Female	61(42.65)	49(34.26)	28(19.58)	05(3.49)	143 (58.36)
Total	96(39.18)	87(60.83)	48(19.59)	14(5.71)	245(100)
Chi square:4.16 & P value: 0.24 (> 0.05)					

By far prevalence of hypertension among age groups is concerned majority of patients belonging to age group 60-69 years were found to be diastolic hypertensive (24.46%) ($P < 0.05$). Whereas more or less equal distribution of prevalence was found in 70 & above age groups for systolic & diastolic hypertension ($P < 0.05$). Overall diastolic hypertension prevalence was more than systolic hypertension ($P > 0.05$). (Table: 3)

Table 3: Age group wise distribution of Systolic & Diastolic hypertension

Age group (in years)	Systolic Hypertension	Diastolic Hypertension	Total	Chi square	P value
60-69	22 (11.7)	46(24.46)	188 (46.73)	10.33	0.0013
70 & above	12(21.05)	16(28.07)	57 (23.26)	0.76	0.383
Total	34(13.87)	62 (25.30)	245 (100)	10.16	0.0014

By far prevalence of hypertension among gender is concerned majority of male patients were found to be diastolic hypertensive (28.43%) ($P < 0.05$). More of less same trend was found among female patients. (Table: 4)

Table 4: Gender wise distribution of Systolic & Diastolic hypertension.

Gender	Systolic Hypertension	Diastolic Hypertension	Total	Chi square	P value
Male	13(12.7)	29(28.43)	102(41.63)	7.72	0.0054
female	21(14.68)	33(23.07)	3(58.36)	.29	.698
Total	34(13.8)	62(25.30)	245(100)	10.30	0.0013

Discussion

The prevalence of hypertension ranged from 5-15% between 1960-1990 It had increased to 20-36% in the past decade [12]. The factors which were attributable to this rising trend were the rapid urbanization, lifestyle changes, dietary changes and the increased life expectancy. The high prevalence of hypertension (44.46%) in the current study, confirmed this increasing trend. A compatible prevalence of hypertension was reported (46%) in a study which was conducted among the outdoor patients of an urban health center of Kolkata [13].

This observational study was conducted on elderly Patients (Age 60 years & above) visited the rural health and training center of JLNMC, Bhagalpur. During the study period a total of 245 patients visited the health facility. This study has found out that age and gender was not significantly associated with systolic blood pressure. More or less same kind of observation was also noticed with diastolic blood pressure where age and gender were not significantly associated. Prakash J et al also found significant association of hypertension with the age group in a Rohtak based study. [14]

Similarly, statistically significant association of hypertension with age group was observed in studies by Abu-Aisha et al., [15], Ganesh et al., [16], Ramakrishnan et al., [17], Dhungana et al., [18] among general population of age group 18-70 years in

Kathmandu, Nagammanavar et al., [19] among bank employees of Bellary city, Karnataka, and Ismail et al. [20].

The proportion of hypertension, as well as the mean systolic and diastolic blood pressures, were found to increase steadily with an increase in age. These findings were coherent with those which had been reported in the studies which were conducted among the urban adults of Mumbai [21] and Lucknow [22]. Such changes of blood pressure with age, might be due to the changes in the vascular system. Cross-sectional surveys, as well as prospective observational cohort studies, have consistently demonstrated a positive relation between the age and blood pressure in most of the populations, with diverse geographical, cultural and socioeconomic characteristics Present study has found out that hypertension (both systolic & Diastolic variant) was more prevalent among age group of 60 to 69 years. More or less same kind of observation was also noticed in a study conducted by Mehmood SE et al. [9]

Diastolic hypertension was found to be more prevalent among elderly age groups ($P < 0.05$). A study conducted at Rohtak by Prakash J et al [14] & study conducted by Mehmood SE et al [9] at Lucknow has found age as an independent significant predictor of hypertension. Prevalence of diastolic hypertension among male patients was found to be almost double as compared to systolic hypertension ($P < 0.05$). Almost similar observations was found among female

patients ($P > 0.05$). Study conducted at Lucknow [9] has found prevalence of hypertension more among females contrary to our study.

They have also found that gender is not a significant predictor of hypertension. Comparable observations (48.4% in females and 47.5% in males) were reported among the urban adults of Mumbai [21]. A female preponderance was also observed by Kabir et al., among the outdoor patients of Dhaka Medical College. In contrast, a greater proportion of hypertension was observed among males (42.9%) as compared to females (34.2%), among the urban adults of Lucknow, India [22].

Conclusion

Hypertension was found to be highly prevalent among the outdoor patients of Rural Health & Training Centre of Bihar. This study warrants the need of an early detection of hypertension, which can be accomplished by a periodic screening of the people, regularly at the hospital as well as at the community levels.

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